

THE STRATEGIES USED BY EFL PROSPECTIVE TEACHER DEVELOP THEIR TPACK

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Abstract: The high level of Technological Content Knowledge (TCK) among prospective student teachers in their TPACK profile has significant implications. This indicates that these students possessed a strong understanding of how to effectively integrate technology into their teaching practices, specifically in relation to the content they were teaching. This proficiency in TCK enables them to utilize technological tools and resources in a purposeful and pedagogically sound manner, enhancing the overall quality of instruction in the classroom. As a result, these prospective teachers are better equipped to meet the demands of the digital age and provide meaningful and engaging learning experiences for their future students. However, it is important for them to continue developing their pedagogical and content knowledge along with their technological skills to ensure a comprehensive and well-rounded TPACK profile..

Key Words: Whatsapp, Online learning, Media

INTRODUCTION

Teachers play an important role in education in the twenty-first century, often known as the digital era. Teachers' challenges in the digital era are becoming more difficult and complex as time passes. Every instructor must be able to respond to changing times by constantly

updating material. To be more specific, in this all-digital world, every instructor must be able to adapt by adjusting learning techniques to meet the times and needs of students. The digital era has altered the world's perceptions of politics, economy, and social issues, including education. The digital era is heavily influencing the growth of the world of education, particularly in the field of education. As a result, teachers, as one of the education stakeholders, play a critical role in the learning process in the digital era.

To effectively integrate ICT, teachers must understand about technology, content, pedagogy, and the interrelationship of these areas (Nordin et al., 2013). As a result, the TPACK (Technological Pedagogical and Content Knowledge) model provides an important theoretical foundation for this research. TPACK refers to the incorporation of ICT into instruction. According to (Koehler et al., 2013), TPACK is a type of emergent knowledge that includes all three "core" components (content, pedagogy, and technology). These three components categorized into several and summarized such as Technological Knowledge (TK), Content Knowledge (CK), Pedagogical Knowledge (PK), Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK), Technological Pedagogical Knowledge (TPK), and Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK).

LITERATURE REVIEW

TPACK Framework

The TPACK framework expands on Shulman (1986,1987) PCK descriptions to describe how teachers' understanding of educational technologies and PCK interact with one another to produce effective technology-assisted teaching. Afterward, Mishra and Koehler created

a framework that includes technology integration. The model created by Mishra and Koehler is a development of the model or framework introduced by Shulman in 1986 called PCK (pedagogical content knowledge). The reason behind the development of this new framework is the fact that "new technologies have changed the classroom situation or have the potential to change it". From Mishra and Koehler's point of view, technology provides space for explanations, representations, analogies, and demonstrations that make the subject matter easier to understand for students but at the same time, they argue that technology is different from content and content description. They identify and define each component and then analyze content, pedagogy, and technology in pairs to understand the intersections between them. Thompson (2007) changed TPACK into TPACK. The new name, TPACK, doesn't just mean adding a vowel "A" to make it easier to pronounce. Its deeper implication is to emphasize the necessity of three kinds of knowledge, content knowledge, pedagogical knowledge and technology knowledge, to form a whole through interaction.

TPACK, Technological Pedagogical and Content Knowledge, is a framework to provide educators' views and knowledge in designing lesson plans so that a meaningful and meaningful change process occurs by teachers for students. Technology is the knowledge that educators need to have as a provision to teach students so that students can interpret the learning process more easily and better and of course in accordance with the times. TPACK or TPACK is a framework that describes teachers' understanding of the interrelated interactions between technology, content, and pedagogy (Koehler et al., 2004).

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According to the TPACK model that can be seen obviously in figure 2.1, there are three main components of teachers' knowledge: 1) Content, 2) Pedagogy, and 3) Technology. Equally important to the model are the interactions among these bodies of knowledge, represented as PCK (Pedagogical Content Knowledge), TCK (Technological Content Knowledge), TPK (Technological Pedagogical Knowledge), and TPACK (Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge).

Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK)

TPACK is a form of emergent knowledge that encompasses all three "core" components (content, pedagogy, and technology).

Knowledge of technological pedagogical content develops from interactions between content, pedagogy, and technology knowledge. TPACK, which underpins really meaningful and deeply skilled teaching using technology, is distinct from the understanding of any of the three ideas separately. TPACK, on the other hand, is the foundation of effective teaching with technology, requiring an understanding of the representation of concepts using technologies; pedagogical techniques that use technologies in constructive ways to teach content; knowledge of what makes concepts difficult or easy to learn, and how technology can help redress some of the problems that students face; knowledge of students' prior knowledge and theories of epistemology; and knowledge of how technologies can be used to help redress some of the problems that students face (Koehler et al., 2013). The figure and explanation above are a representation of the elements of T (technology), (Pedagogy) and C (content) which together produce a knowledge construct of technology content. It is useful to provide a reference for how the three elements are related and mutually support each other. In other words, the above is a description and explanation of how a subject matter is transformed by the application of technology. T and P together describe the pedagogical knowledge of technology, or knowledge of how technology can support pedagogical goals. The existence of knowledge and introduction of technology in a learning process creates new concepts and requires the development of dynamic transactional relationships between the three components suggested by the TPACK or TPCK framework.

Within this framework, many studies argue that teachers should be educated to integrate knowledge of technology, pedagogy,

and content in teacher preparation programs (Association for Computers in Mathematics and Science Teaching (U.S.) et al., 2010; Niess, 2005). However, we are not aware of any research that particularly focuses on how to educate prospective teacher teachers to construct integrative knowledge for technology integration. More importantly, they (and practising teachers) need to be able to use this professional knowledge to design learning activities, or put into place relevant instructional practices, for the specific children they teach (Oakley, 2011).

TPACK in New Normal Era

The "new normal era" refers to a period characterized by significant and lasting changes in various aspects of society and daily life, often resulting from major disruptive events or circumstances. It signifies a shift from previous norms and practices to a new set of circumstances, behaviors, and expectations that become the accepted standard. The term gained prominence during the COVID-19 pandemic, as it describes the adjustments and adaptations made by individuals, organizations, and communities to mitigate the impact of the virus (Viner et al., 2020). This includes changes in social interactions, work arrangements, educational systems, travel, and health care practices.

TPACK in the new era encompasses the application of pedagogical strategies that promote active engagement and collaborative learning experiences among students. Teachers with strong TPACK skills design online activities and assignments that foster student interaction, critical thinking, and problem solving (Niess, 2005). They create opportunities for peer collaboration, group projects, and online discussions, thus ensuring that students are actively involved in the learning process (Archambault et al. 2010).

According to Juwandani et al. (2022) research titled "Blended Learning Strategy in the New Normal Era using the TPACK Competency Study," it has been emphasized that in the context of the new normal era, it is crucial for teachers to integrate technology effectively or implement the Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) framework into the teaching and learning process. The new normal era, characterized by the COVID-19 pandemic and its subsequent impact on education, has necessitated a shift in instructional practices and the adoption of innovative approaches to ensure continued learning. In this era, where traditional face-to-face teaching has been disrupted, the integration of technology has become essential for facilitating remote or blended learning environments.

The TPACK framework guides teachers in making informed decisions regarding the selection, utilization, and integration of digital tools, pedagogical strategies, and subject-specific content knowledge. It enables teachers to leverage technology effectively to enhance their learning experience, promote student engagement, and facilitate meaningful knowledge construction. By integrating technology and TPACK into the teaching process, teachers can employ various instructional methods that cater to different learning styles and preferences. Blended learning, which combines online and offline elements, has gained prominence as an effective strategy in the new normal era (Juwandani et al., 2022). It allows for flexibility, personalized learning experiences, and the integration of various digital resources such as multimedia materials, online collaboration tools, and interactive assessments. Furthermore, the selection of appropriate teaching methods in the new normal era significantly affects

students' understanding and engagement in the learning process. Teachers must employ pedagogical approaches that align with the unique challenges and opportunities of remote or blended learning environments.

They should design activities that foster active participation, critical thinking, and collaborative problem solving among students. Additionally, formative assessment techniques should be utilized to gauge students' progress and provide timely feedback, thereby enhancing their learning experiences (Juwandani et al., 2022). Alfarouqy's (2022) research study titled "Technological, Pedagogical, and Content Knowledge (TPACK) Profile of Class IV Teachers of SDN Batok Bali in Thematic Learning in The New Normal Era" sheds light on the significance of technology integration in education during the new normal era. The study highlights that in this era, where traditional face-to-face instruction has been disrupted, utilizing technology has become crucial for effective and engaging learning experiences. By incorporating technology tools and resources into thematic learning, teachers can not only increase students' enthusiasm for learning, but also enhance the efficiency of the learning process.

One of the key advantages of integrating technology in the new normal era is the ability to streamline and simplify various aspects of learning. Technology enables teachers to go beyond traditional instructional methods by incorporating multimedia elements such as video playback or PowerPoint presentations, which can effectively replace extensive reliance on textbooks. This allows students to visualize concepts, engage with interactive content, and grasp complex ideas more easily. Moreover, the use of technology in thematic learning can provide a dynamic and interactive learning environment. Using digital tools,

teachers can create virtual simulations, interactive quizzes, and collaborative online activities that foster student engagement and active participation. This interactive approach encourages students to play an active role in their learning processes, promoting critical thinking, problem-solving, and creativity.

In the new normal era, TPACK (Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge) plays a crucial role in integrating technology into the learning process. Teachers with a strong TPACK can wisely select and use technology to enhance student engagement, facilitate deep understanding, and promote skills relevant to the digital age. However, challenges such as technological infrastructure readiness and the need for teacher knowledge updates must be addressed. Efforts such as providing adequate technology facilities, enhancing teachers' digital literacy, and allocating sufficient time for feedback and student interaction can support the effective implementation of TPACK in the new normal era.

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and student interaction can support the effective implementation of TPACK in the new normal era.

Research Method

The purpose of this research is to figure out the how are EFL prospective teachers' TPACK in the new normal era, how do EFL prospective teachers develop their TPACK, and the challenges do the EFL prospective teachers experience during their TPACK development so that the researcher decides to apply qualitative research. Thus, for this purpose, a qualitative research is chosen as the research method used in this research.

Result and Discussion

The Strategies Used by EFL Prospective Teacher Develop Their TPACK

One of the key factors in developing Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) among EFL prospective teachers is the implementation of effective strategies. EFL prospective teachers employ various strategies to enhance their TPACK by integrating technological knowledge with pedagogical and content knowledge. These strategies contribute to their professional growth and readiness to use technology effectively in English language teaching. Similar to the previous findings, in this discussion, the researcher will outline the strategies employed by EFL prospective teachers in developing TPACK, categorized into three parts: high, average, and low.

1. The Strategies Used by High Level EFL Prospective Teacher

At the high level, the researcher identified some strategies mentioned by the respondents in developing TPACK, those are the habit of utilizing digital learning platforms, which naturally includes the availability of facilities, and the optimization of digital learning. Other strategies include attending training or workshops, incorporating various teaching methods, and more.

a. Familiarize with digital learning platforms

Multiple studies have discovered and documented that one commonly employed strategy for enhancing Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) is the cultivation of familiarity and proficiency in utilizing digital learning platforms (Farhadi & Öztürk, 2023b; Harris & Harris, n.d, 2016; Pradita et al., 2023; Sari et al., 2021; Syamdianita & Cahyono, 2021; Taopan, 2020). The strategy for developing TPACK through adaptation to technology involves integrating technological tools and resources into pedagogical practices. This approach focuses on fostering educators' ability to effectively leverage technology to enhance content knowledge, pedagogical techniques, and understanding how technology can best support learning outcomes. These findings are corroborated by the insights shared by interviewee 1, who highlighted their adeptness with digital learning platforms, enthusiasm for exploring various platforms, and proactive endeavors to optimize the utilization of these platforms.

I would say the best one is Zotero, for all of the students in the classroom I can say, why? Because first students are familiar with that... (Interviewee 1)

I love to try, I love to explore, so unlike maybe some of my friends are not super brave enough to try every single button in the platform, I myself love to explore... (interviewee 1)

This is supported by interviewee 2, who is at the same level and also mentioned the familiarity and optimization of digital learning platforms. We can utilize all these features for digital learning because we do not need to install any apps.

All we need is an Internet connection, and it does not take up much storage on students' devices. It is also easier for teachers to manage data with the help of Google, including organizing assessments and collecting assignments using Google Classroom. It allows us to track who is late and who is active (interviewee 2)

We continue to use Google, specifically Google Classroom, because it provides built-in features for monitoring student progress. It has its own assessment features for grading student work (Interviewee 2)

Several strategies or approaches can be used to develop TPACK, such as software-based, computer-adaptive, and personalized approaches, all of which represent the newest approaches to TPACK development (Harris & Harris, n.d. 2016). In addition to adaptation being necessary in TPACK development, students also need access to adequate digital learning tools or technological devices to cultivate familiarity with them. The utilization of adequate facilities plays a crucial role in the development of TPACK. Access to suitable facilities enables educators to effectively integrate technology into their teaching practices and to enhance their technological pedagogical content knowledge. By providing resources such as well-equipped computer labs, interactive whiteboards, educational software, and reliable Internet connectivity, the facilitation of TPACK development is

greatly supported. These resources enable educators to explore and implement innovative instructional strategies that leverage technology to enhance content delivery, engage students and promote meaningful learning experiences. Syamdianita & Cahyono (2021) in their research on the EFL (English as a Foreign Language) preservice teachers' experiences in designing and implementing teaching materials by using the Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) framework through the Learning by Design (LBD) approach stated that to apply TPACK, teachers must have facilities, for example, a laptop, a projector, and an electricity network because TPACK involves technology to implement the TPACK framework.

As mentioned by several sources, Kahoot is used quite often. A research about investigated the Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) level and needs of prospective teachers through a convergent parallel design by Farhadi & Öztürk (2023), Kahoot as the most frequently utilized platform for assessing the performance of learners with their peers in a stress-free environment. Furthermore, aligned with specific purposes such as comprehension, assessment, learning, and feedback, technological applications and devices were profited from in EFL classrooms. Based on the interviews conducted, it was found that EFL prospective teachers utilize a wide range of digital learning platforms beyond those initially mentioned. These platforms have gained popularity in academic settings because of their effectiveness in facilitating language learning and teaching. According to Pradita et al. (2023) prospective teachers apply some of technology applications or digital learning platforms, including Google

Classroom, Quizziz, and YouTube, to learn English. This technology application helps prospective teachers in teaching and learning processes.

b. Participate in Workshops or Training

In this research, another strategy used by EFL prospective teachers to enhance their Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) in high level was to participate in workshops or training specifically focused on TPACK (Harris & Harris, n.d.; Ismaeel & Al Mulhim, 2022a; Najjari et al., 2021; Sari et al., 2021). Workshops and training sessions provide opportunities for prospective EFL teachers to acquire knowledge and practical skills related to integrating technology into their pedagogical practices. Attending training or workshops on TPACK development holds significant importance for prospective English teachers. Through such training, students can enhance their understanding of the TPACK concept, which involves integrating technology with content knowledge and pedagogy. In these training sessions, they will learn about various relevant technology tools and applications for English language instruction as well as develop effective technological skills. Additionally, TPACK training allows prospective teachers to update their knowledge of the latest developments in educational technology, including new trends and best practices for using technology for language learning. Thus, through TPACK training or workshops, prospective teachers can enhance their preparation to tackle the challenges of teaching in the digital era and ensure effective technology use in English language instruction. Cahyani and Cahyono (2012) in Sari et al. (2021) stated that a teacher who is not skillful in using technology will join some workshops and training in recognizing new technology.

It may cause the teacher to have more time to see and observe the technology supporting the learning process. This was also mentioned by Qasem and Viswanathapp (2016) in Ismaeel & Al Mulhim (2022) which present a blended ICT knowledge training to improve teachers' teaching competencies based on the TPACK model. There are several reasons why it is essential for prospective teachers to attend workshops or training sessions to enhance their knowledge of technology. These workshops or training sessions assist students in acquiring the necessary knowledge and skills to master educational technology, including the utilization of relevant software or digital tools for instructional purposes. By participating in these events, they can improve their competence in using technology within an educational context that involves strategies for integrating technology into the curriculum and learning activities. Additionally, these workshops and training sessions provide opportunities for prospective teachers to interact with other education professionals, allowing them to share experiences and expand their professional networks. This interaction enables students to gain new insights into the latest developments in the use of technology in education. As mentioned by Interviewee 2 in this research during the interview conducted with the researchers.

First of all, provide training first before the introduction. Even though someone might already know or be familiar with Google, not everyone will necessarily understand when asked for examples of using Google in that way. In the initial training, focus on introducing and teaching the basics. Two face-to-face meetings are sufficient for the initial introduction, with each session lasting for a class period. After that, we can schedule further learning sessions.

Overall, attending workshops or training sessions equips prospective teachers with the knowledge, skills, and professional connections necessary to effectively incorporate technology into their teaching practices. This finding is supported by Qasem and Viswanathappa (2016), Ersoy et al. (2016), and Maeng et al. (2013) in Ismaeel & Al Mulhim (2022), who confirm that training through extensive technology applications can enable prospective teachers to use technology appropriately depending on the context and content. Ansyari, n.d. (2013) who reported that TPACK training program assisted teachers in expanding the perception of practical skills they need for technology integration. Also, the findings of by Bradshaw (2002) research showed a positive effect by implementing the training course for EFL teachers who engaged in professional development practices such as “theory, demonstration, practice, and follow-up” and as a result, EFL teachers were more willing to convey their technological skills in the teaching process.

c. Learning Method

The next strategy utilized by EFL prospective teachers in developing TPACK is related to the application of teaching methods. Based on the data obtained by the researchers, the respondents mentioned various methods such as the direct method or learning-by-doing, Communicative Language Teaching (CLT), and conventional learning. This is supported by Syamdianita and Cahyono (2021), who stated that respondents used the direct method in their research on TPACK implementation. Najjari et al. (2021) mentioned that ‘learning-by-doing’ assisted teachers in understanding that successful technology integration is possible, leading to the implementation of

technology integration by teachers. As stated in the following interview quote,

Also I love real life implementation, I think most students love this, real-life implementation in teaching methodology in ELT related to the activity that can be done by the teacher to the students but the lecturer teach us how to do it (interviewee 1)

Interviewee 1 stated that practice-based learning, or learning-by-doing, can enhance TPACK. In this context, they referred to it as real-life implementation. A similar finding was also observed for interviewee 2.

To be more specific, what I forgot to mention earlier is the concept of "trial and error." This means that we continue to try and experiment while being guided by face-to-face interactions (interviewee 2)

Similar to interviewee 1, interviewee 2 also acknowledged that practice-based learning or learning by doing can improve their TPACK. In this case, they referred to it as "trial and error".

Regarding the use of Communicative Language Teaching (CLT), respondents in the research by Syamdianita and Cahyono (2021) also mentioned CLT as one of the methods they used. However, despite the widespread use of technology in various fields, particularly education, where technology optimization greatly aids learning, many teachers, especially prospective teachers, still struggle to effectively and optimally utilize technology for various reasons. This

is supported by the research conducted by Sari et al. (2021), who stated that the use of technology seemed to require longer time allocation for a lesson, and respondents in the research indicated that a technology-enhanced lesson is not a simple process and could continue with a traditional teaching approach. On the other hand, the results of the research conducted by Pradita et al. (2023) indicated that prospective teachers understand TPACK in terms of echnology for learning methods, such as discovery learning, cooperative learning, question and answer, problem-solving, discussion, and problem-based learning.

Research has shown that the learning methods adopted by prospective English language teacher candidates have a significant influence on the development of TPACK (Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge). TPACK refers to the knowledge teachers possess in integrating technology, pedagogy, and content into their teaching practices. Mishra & Koehler (2006) emphasized the importance of students' experiences of using technology in a learning context. Prospective teachers engaged in learning methods that encouraged the use of technology, such as practical training in using instructional software or e-learning platforms, tended to develop stronger technological knowledge. They had the opportunity to become acquainted with and master relevant tools and resources for English language instruction such as interactive applications, software, and other digital resources. With the development of technological knowledge, teachers can more effectively integrate technology into their instructional practices. In addition to technological knowledge, learning methods influence the development of prospective teachers' pedagogical knowledge. According to Ertmer et al. (2012), practical experience in implementing effective teaching strategies through student-centered learning methods can help students develop a solid pedagogical

knowledge base. They learn about active, collaborative, and student-centered learning strategies and how to apply them in the context of English language instruction. Students also gain a better understanding of effective classroom management, authentic assessment, and constructive feedback. Content knowledge is an essential component of the development of TPACK. Prospective English language teachers must have a strong understanding of the content and subject matter they teach. Through learning methods that emphasize mastery of content and the application of English language knowledge in real-world situations, students can develop in-depth content knowledge. They studied language structures, speaking, writing, reading, listening skills, and cultural aspects related to English. With strong content understanding, they can appropriately integrate technology into English language teaching by using suitable tools aligned with learning goals and student characteristics. In the context of TPACK development, Koehler & Mishra (2009) emphasized the complex interaction between technological, pedagogical, and content knowledge in English language learning. Learning methods that integrate these aspects effectively empower prospective teachers to navigate through the dynamic challenges of the educational landscape.

Conclusion

Another important finding of several studies is that there is a large correlation between the TCK, TPK, and TPACK constructs, which prompted researchers to question the peculiarities of these three TPACK domains. Referring to TPACK's weaknesses in terms of precision and heuristic values, they concluded that TPACK may be theoretically effective but provides limited practical benefits for teachers, researchers, and administrators.

The high level of Technological Content Knowledge (TCK) among prospective student teachers in their TPACK profile has significant implications. This indicates that these students possessed a strong understanding of how to effectively integrate technology into their teaching practices, specifically in relation to the content they were teaching. This proficiency in TCK enables them to utilize technological tools and resources in a purposeful and pedagogically sound manner, enhancing the overall quality of instruction in the classroom. As a result, these prospective teachers are better equipped to meet the demands of the digital age and provide meaningful and engaging learning experiences for their future students. However, it is important for them to continue developing their pedagogical and content knowledge along with their technological skills to ensure a comprehensive and well-rounded TPACK profile.

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